
To rectify Alzheimer's disease etiology, excessive mitochondrial division might be stopped or mitophagy might be promoted

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Abstract: In both in vitro and in vivo Alzheimer's disease (AD) models, mitochondrial dysfunction is a crucial feature that limits neuronal activity and results in A and phosphorylated Tau toxicity. To rectify AD etiology, excessive mitochondrial division might be stopped or mitophagy might be promoted. However, there are still unexplained mysteries surrounding the formation of senile plaques and NFTs, and the pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease lacks fundamental unifying principles. Some scientists believe A toxicity and Tau toxicity are upstream processes in mitochondrial dysfunction, while others feel it is a downstream chain of events involving abnormal mitochondria. There are several mitophagy mechanisms for the clearance of dead mitochondria in PINK1 signaling; some are regulated by Parkin, while others are not. Drp1, Mfn1/2, PINK1, or Parkin, according to some researchers, have no role in mitophagy cleaning dysfunctional mitochondria; so, additional study is needed to solve the puzzle of mitophagy signaling pathways for clearing dead mitochondria and conserving high-quality mitochondria. Therapeutic techniques targeting mitophagy activity might be useful in reversing AD etiology.

1. Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most prevalent neurodegenerative and dementia illness worldwide. It has been defined pathologically by extraneuronal amyloid deposition, also known as senile plaques, and intraneuronal deposition of neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) since 1901. (Kandimalla et al., 2011, 2012, 2013, Kandimalla, Manczak et al., 2016). Mitochondrial dysfunction, imbalance in mitochondrial fission and fusion, mitochondrial fragmentation, derailment of mitochondrial biogenesis, synaptic loss, microglial activation, loss of neuronal polarity, irregular neuronal apoptosis, calcium homeostasis deregulation through N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDAR), and failure in cellular resuscitation are the main cellular mechanisms that cause AD pathology (Kandimalla & Reddy, 2017; Kandimalla, Manczak et al., 2016, 2017; Kerr et al., 2017).

Mitochondria are usually believed and regarded to be the cell's powerhouse, but this is not confined to neuronal cells. Mitochondria use reduced nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NADH)/reduced flavin adenine dinucleotide (FADH) reducing equivalents to create adenosine triphosphates (ATPs) via oxidative phosphorylation (OXOPHOS). According to earlier estimates, the electron transport chain creates 12 ATPs and 10 ATPs according to recent calculations. One molecule of glucose oxidized produces 38 ATPs (old calculations) or 32 ATPs (new calculations) (new calculations). Similarly, according to old and recent estimations, palmitic acid oxidation yields 129 or 106 ATPs. The ATP: NADH+H⁺ and ATP: FADH ratios were previously calculated as 3 and 2, respectively. The real ratios, however, are 2.5 and 1.5, which have been factored into the revised computation. When one molecule of

glucose is oxidized, the reducing equivalents are likewise created in mitochondria. ATP energy is required for crucial brain activities, as well as neuronal transmission and the formation of strong synaptic connections in learning and memory (Swerdlow & Khan 2004). In the adult hippocampus, mitochondria are also important for the construction and maintenance of synapses, as well as the development of neural plasticity through axonal tubule polymerization (Kerr et al., 2017; Reddy et al., 2004). Mitochondria are subjected to numerous insults and lose their cellular functions, resulting in a decrease in the production of cellular ATP and an increase in the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which can damage lipids in the outer and inner mitochondrial membranes, proteins, and nucleic acids (Kerr et al., 2017). Finally, it has an impact on the quality, health, biogenesis, fragmentation, and synaptic plasticity of mitochondria. Specifically, soluble amyloid (A) oligomers and phosphorylated Tau compromise mitochondrial integrity (Buée et al., 2000; Kandimalla, Manczak et al., 2016; Manczak et al., 2016; Manczak et al., 2016). Recent research has linked the interaction of A42, which is generated by secretases from amyloid precursor protein (APP), and phosphorylated Tau, with Drp1 and altered mitochondrial function (s), such as cytochrome C oxidase activity, ATP generation, and free radical clearance (Manczak et al., 2012, 2016). Excessive calorie consumption and lack of physical exercise, on the other hand, have been linked to mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress in recent research (Gwon et al., 2012; Mattson, 2012; Schafer et al., 2015; SimsRobinson et al., 2010; Walker & Harrison, 2015).

The aberrant processing of APP and hyperphosphorylation of Tau proteins may result from mitochondrial dysfunction caused by oxidative stress (Reddy, 2006; Reddy & Beal, 2008). The findings of the study indicated that mitochondrial malfunction can result in the generation of A peptides as a result of aberrant APP processing (Schafer et al., 2015). Tau is a protein that is linked to microtubules in the cellular skeleton and plays an important role in AD pathogenesis. Tau also promotes microtubule polymerization and stability, as well as the movement of mitochondria, lysosomes, vesicles, and other organelles. However, when Tau is hyperphosphorylated by phosphatases and proteases under oxidative stress, microtubules become destabilized, which leads to the derailment of transporting organelles. Impaired mitochondria may promote neuronal death by activating caspase 3 and cytochrome C before creating full AD symptoms (Buée et al., 2000; Gong et al., 2010; Hoglinger et al., 2005; Mattson et al., 1997). As a result, the majority of these studies suggested that mitochondrial dysfunction might be a precursor to Tau and A diseases (Briston & Hicks, 2018). As a result, maintaining a healthy mitochondrial number is critical for neural function. Mitophagy and autophagy signaling pathways would clear dead or dysfunctional mitochondria with the help of PTEN-induced kinase 1 (PINK1), nuclear dot protein 52kDa (NDP52), p62/SQSTM1, optineurin (OPTN), autophagy-related gene 5 (ATG5), Bcl2 interacting proteinlike 3 (BNIP3 also known as NiX), FUN14 domain containing 1 (FUNDC1), microtubule (Briston & Hicks, 2018; Kerr et al., 2017; Kumar et al., 2018; Manczak et al., 2018).

Mitochondrial dynamics, mitophagy, and autophagy are all necessary for neuronal survival because they regulate their activities. Mitophagy and autophagy, on the other hand, are harmed in Alzheimer's disease and other neurodegenerative illnesses. The focus of this review study is on dynamic equilibrium, Parkin-dependent or Parkin-independent mitophagy, and autophagy in the development of Alzheimer's disease.

2. Dysfunction of the mitochondrial system

Mitochondria are a doublemembrane subcellular organelle whose abnormalities contribute to neurodegenerative disorders. NFTs are deposited in intraneuron while senile plaques are deposited in extraneuron in patients with Alzheimer's disease. Mitochondria are unable to produce sufficient quantities of energy in the early stages of AD due to A peptides and phosphorylated Tau, and hence defective mitochondria eventually generate excessive production of ROS (Cai & Tammineni, 2016; Hoglinger et al., 2005). The oxidative damage of cell and mitochondrial membranes is caused by A and phosphorylated Tau inception. Furthermore, because the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle and OXOPHOS adequacy is fully dependent on the adequacy of the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle and OXOPHOS, both in healthy and sick brains, oxidative stress may have detrimental consequences on neuronal survival. 4hydroxytrans2nonenal (HNE), hydroxides, superoxides, peroxides, nitriles, and 2methoxy estradiol are all produced by mitochondrial membrane lipids, proteins, and nucleic acids. These are later implicated in mtDNA oxidative damage, which leads to an imbalance in mitochondrial dynamics (Cai & Tammineni, 2016; Hoglinger et al., 2005; Mattson et al., 1997; Moreira et al., 2006).

ROS is normally neutralized in healthy brains by enzymes such as catalases, cathepsins, superoxide peroxidase/reductase, thioredoxin reductase, and peroxiredoxin.

When the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) exceeds the capability of ROS clearance enzymes to neutralize them, oxidative stress develops, which causes oxidative stress and eventually destroys neuronal cells by decreasing mitochondrial function (Cai & Tammineni, 2016; Manczak et al., 2011, 2016; Manczak & Reddy, 2012; Kandimalla, Manczak et al., 2016; Kandimalla & Reddy, 2016). Mitochondrial fusion/fission that maintains healthy mitochondria levels mitigates oxidative stress, whereas an increase in HNE concentration disrupts autophagy, exacerbating mitochondrial health and increasing ROS, one of the molecular markers of oxidative stress that leads to amyloid accumulation in AD. The use of HNE as a nonenzymatic lysosome inhibitor was linked to a reduction in mitochondrial oxygen consumption rate owing to posttranslational changes of key signaling and enzyme function residues, according to a study (Dalleau et al., 2013; Redmann et al., 2018). Furthermore, cortical primary neurons treated with chloroquine (lysosome inhibitor) in the presence of LC3I, LC3II, and p62 showed a decrease of clearance capacity (in the presence of p62), which was validated by mitochondrial length Zen measurements. The use of a blue polygon curve tool revealed a reduction in mitochondrial length, indicating a lack of mitophagic activity and increased mitochondria fragmentation (Redmann et al., 2018). Dodson et al. (2017) recently revealed that lower doses of 4HNE (510 M) activate autophagy whereas higher values (15 M) block it. The greater concentration is also linked to mitochondrial dysfunction and changes in dynamic protein levels (Dodson et al., 2017). Medeiros and coworkers (2018) used DNA DAPI staining and fluorescent live cell imaging to show that mtDNA synthesis success was dependent on autophagy, as well as an increase in mitochondria fragmentation in response to stress, which disrupted autophagy and eventually led to decreased mtDNA quantity (Medeiros et al., 2018).

The amount of A peptides accumulated inside the mitochondria, as well as mitochondrial malfunction, was linked to the severity of the cognitive impairments. It has been suggested that A peptides are important in the development of mitochondrial dysfunction. The electron transport chain (ETC), mitochondrial transport, mitochondrial targeted peptide MTP131 (mMTP), and calcium homeostasis are all negatively affected by accumulated A peptides. The A peptides reach the mitochondria by MAM or the outer membrane translocase (TOM) (Cai & Jeong, 2020). Mitophagy and autophagy protein signals, as well as mitochondrial

fission/fusion balance, mitochondrial biogenesis pathways, ubiquitin proteasomal pathways, and mitophagy and autophagy protein signals, all influence the quality of newly generated mitochondria. Various researchers have convincingly demonstrated the biological processes behind A peptides' mitochondrial toxicity. Manczak et al. (2011) discovered mitochondrial damage and its consequences in neuronal damage in postmortem brain samples of AD mice, and validated Drp1 interactions with A42, APP, and phosphorylated Tau. As a result, the authors validated Drp1 protein's critical role in AD pathogenesis (Manczak et al., 2011; Manczak & Reddy, 2012). Manczak and Reddy (2012) discovered that decreased Drp1 protects against mitochondrial and synaptic deficits in 2012.

In the Tau (P301L) mouse model, Kandimalla, Manczak, et al. (2016) found reduced mitochondrial functions, abnormalities in mitochondrial dynamics, biogenesis, loss of synaptic functions, and fragmented mitochondria. Reduced Drp1 was used to repair the defects caused by degraded mitochondrial and synaptic processes, and mitochondrial dynamics were studied utilizing mitochondrial fission proteins, Drp1, Fis1, mitochondrial fusion proteins, Mfn1, Mfn2, and optic atrophy 1 proteins (Opa1). Peroxisome proliferator activated receptor coactivator 1 alpha (PGC1), nuclear respiratory factor 1 (Nrf1), nuclear respiratory factor 2 (Nrf2), and transcription factor A, mitochondrial biogenesis were studied in terms of mRNA and protein expression (Tfam). Synaptophysin and postsynaptic density protein 95 (PSD95) expression levels were measured to investigate synaptic functions. Finally, mitochondrial functions were represented by measuring cellular ATP levels, HNE, peroxide levels, and Drp1 GTPase activity levels. All of these studies were carried out in four different mouse strains: wild type (WT), Drp1 (+/-), Tau (P301L), and TauXDrp1 animals, with the reversal of Tau pathology in double mutant TauXDrp1 animals confirming the protective effect of decreased Drp1 in preventing AD by restoring mitochondrial functioning (Kandimalla, Manczak et al., 2016; Kandimalla & Reddy, 2016). In a separate research, Manczak et al. (2016) found that lower Drp1 protects APP (Tg2576) mice. In comparison to WT mice, scientists found that APP mice have impaired mitochondrial functioning, mitochondrial fragmentation, aberrant mitochondrial biogenesis, and altered mitochondrial and synaptic functioning. Finally, using quantitative real-time PCR, immunoblotting, and staining procedures on cerebral cortex tissue of 6-month-old mice, the scientists were able to correct AD pathology as well as impaired metabolic function. The same researchers discovered altered mitochondrial activities, biogenesis, and synaptic processes, as well as a fission–fusion imbalance, in the hippocampus of 12-month-old Tau (P301L) mice in another study. A Morris water maze test revealed lower hippocampus learning and memory phenotypic alterations, which bolstered these findings (Manczak et al., 2016). In the AD brain, mitochondrial activities are eventually disrupted, which accelerates the disease's development. Based on these findings, it is postulated that mitochondrial malfunction may play a critical role in AD pathogenesis, and that aberrant mitochondrial processes may be downstream targets of A42 and phosphoTau.

3. DRP1 'S role in mitochondria

Mitochondria are dynamic cell organelles that fusion and fission in response to the energy demands of various cells. To preserve cellular homeostasis, the balance between fission and fusion must be maintained. Drp1 is a GTPase protein related to dynamin that promotes mitochondrial fission via Fis1/Mff receptors on the OMM. Drp1 control appears to be important in avoiding Alzheimer's disease (AD), Huntington's disease (HD), Parkinson's disease (PD), amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), diabetes, and cardiovascular disease, according to recent research. Drp1 is required for mitochondrial division and distribution in

axons and dendrites (anterograde and retrograde transport mechanism). Drp1 is also involved in peroxisomal fragmentation, SUMOylation, ubiquitination, and the control of glycogen synthase kinase 3 beta (GSK3). Drp1 is present in the brain, kidney, liver, spleen, heart, testes, skeletal muscle, and hepatocytes, among other places (Giovarelli et al., 2020; Ishihara et al., 2009; Kandimalla, Manczak et al., 2016; Kandimalla & Reddy, 2016; Touvier et al., 2015). Drp1 double KO mice were used in studies to show that this trait is embryonically fatal, suggesting that Drp1 is required throughout development (Wakabayashi et al., 2009). Drp1's involvement and physiological importance in mitochondrial division in brain tissue were described by Ishihara et al. (2009). Drp1 association with phosphorylated Tau, A42, Huntingtin, and synuclein was later discovered, validating the pathogenic involvement of Drp1 protein (Manczak et al., 2011; Manczak & Reddy, 2012, 2015; Reddy & Shirendeb, 2012). Drp1 does not, however, play a pathogenic role in AD, HD, or PD on its own. Drp1 appears to interact with many autophagy proteins and controls neuronal death, according to evidence (Menziez et al., 2015; Nixon, 2013; Rubinsztein et al., 2011). Drp1 activity was reduced by mitochondrial division inhibitor (Mdivi1), SzetoSchiller Peptide (SS31), mitochondrialtargeted antioxidant (MitoQ), 2,3dichloro5,6dicyanobenzoquinone (DDQ) (Kuruva et al., 2017; Manczak et al., 2019; Reddy, Tonk et al., 2017; Wani et al., 2011), or heterozyg Simultaneously, researchers discovered lower levels of H₂O₂, lipid peroxidation, and hazardous compounds such as phosphorylated Tau, A42, and interactions with Drp1 in these investigations (Kandimalla, Manczak et al., 2016; Kandimalla & Reddy, 2016; Manczak et al., 2016). Drp1 has been implicated in the mediation of mitophagy and autophagosomal engulfment for the removal of dead mitochondria (Gomes et al., 2011; Rambold et al., 2011; Tanaka et al., 2010) and the separation of nonfunctional mitochondrial regions for elimination (Gomes et al., 2011; Rambold et al., 2011; Tanaka et al., 2010). (Twig et al., 2008). Parkin-independent mitophagy needs Drp1 and protects the integrity of the mammalian heart and brain, according to Kageyama et al. (2014). Surprisingly, several investigations have found that Drp1 has no involvement in mitophagy (Li et al., 2019; Oliver & Reddy, 2019a; Reddy & Oliver, 2019). When both park-dependent and park-independent pathways control mitophagy with the PINK1/NiX1/BNIP3L/FUNDC1 complex, OMM stability and IMM depolarization occur (Kerr et al., 2017).

The aforementioned sequence of events occurred as a result of excessive mitochondrial fragmentation or mitochondrial function impairment, resulting in the recruitment of PINK1 on OMM to activate mitophagy. However, more research is needed to validate the involvement of Drp1 on PINK1 in controlling mitophagy for the elimination of dead and/or nonfunctional mitochondria subdomains. Drp1 is a target molecule for a number of different proteins and microRNAs (miRs) that regulate mitochondrial dynamics.

4. Mitophagy

Autophagy is the degradation of defective or damaged cell organelles as well as misfolded proteins. Mitophagy, on the other hand, is a specialized type of autophagy that regulates the turnover of defective and damaged mitochondria under a variety of pathological circumstances (Fivenson et al., 2017; Pradeepkiran & Reddy, 2020; Uddin et al., 2019). MartinezLopez et al., 2015; Menziez et al., 2015; Nixon, 2013; Rubinsztein et al., 2011) found that mitophagy/autophagy is required for cell survival and that its malfunction can lead to aging-related illnesses. Mitophagy failure has been linked to a number of neurodegenerative illnesses, including Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, and Huntington's disease. Different pathways, such as PINK1/Parkin dependent and independent

routes, NiX/BNIP3L pathways, and FUNDC1 pathways, are used to carry out mitophagy (Kerr et al., 2017).

4.1 Mitophagy that is PINK1/Parkin dependent

PINK1 is a serine/threonine kinase found in mitochondria that is involved in Parkin-dependent mitophagy. Overexpression of PINK1 promotes mitochondrial fission, whereas inhibition of PINK1 causes excessive mitochondrial fusion in *Drosophila* and human cells, according to a study on PINK1 mutants (Yang et al., 2008). Drp1 phosphorylation determines mitochondrial fission, and before mitophagy, PINK1 and PARKIN collaborate to recruit Drp1 (Buhlman et al., 2014). The TOM and the inner membrane translocase import PINK1 into the OMM in healthy mitochondria (TIM). The Nterminal peptide is integrated into the IMM after being imported and then cleaved by mitochondrial proteases. Ubiquitin protein ligase E3 component nrecognin 1, 2, and 4 (UBR1, UBR2, and UBR4) imports the cleaved Nterminal portion to the cytosol for destruction by E3 ubiquitin ligases (Yamano & Youle, 2013).

Mitochondrial matrix proteases (MMPs) and mitochondrial intramembrane proteases such as presenilin-associated rhomboidlike proteases cleave the C terminus (PARL). As a result, the action of proteases and ubiquitin ligases in healthy mitochondria keeps PINK1 levels low. PINK1 works as a sensor and accumulates in the OMM in response to stress circumstances such as increased ROS levels, depolarized mitochondrial membrane, and higher quantities of misfolded proteins. This causes PINK1 to accumulate in the mitochondrial membrane, causing Parkin to be recruited from the cytosol to the mitochondria. Parkin is an E3 ubiquitin ligase that is inactive in the cytosol until it is phosphorylated by PINK1. Parkin is selectively recruited into defective mitochondria with low membrane potential for mitophagy execution, according to several investigations utilizing chemicals that alter mitochondrial potential (Iguchi et al., 2013; Koentjoro et al., 2017; Koyano & Matsuda, 2015; Lee et al., 2015; Matsuda et al., 2010; Narendra & Youle, 2011; Park et al., 2018; Tanaka et al., 2010). The rate-limiting phase in mitophagy execution is selective Parkin recruitment. PINK1 can also phosphorylate the OMM's ubiquitin chains, allowing Parkin to connect to them. Parkin then ubiquitinates a number of proteins on the OMM. These polyubiquitin chains are subsequently identified by autophagy-associated proteins such as LC3, OPTN, and NDP52, which aid in the fusing of the mitochondrial membrane with the autophagosomal membrane, allowing depolarized mitochondria to be cleared. Researchers discovered the involvement of hexokinase 1 and 2 in Parkin recruiting PINK1 to the OMM of mitochondria, resulting in OMM stability and IMM depolarization to activate mitophagy, in several novel investigations (Gong et al., 2010; McCoy et al., 2014). Mitochondrial E3 ubiquitin protein ligase 1 (MUL1) also clears dead mitochondria in conjunction with the PINK1/Parkin system, and it interestingly compensates for the PINK1/Parkin mitophagy system when it fails to clear dead mitochondria for effective neuronal activities (Vincow et al., 2013; Yun et al., 2014).

Fang et al. (2019) found that activating mitophagy through PINK1/Parkin or DAF16/FOXO dependent pathways in the presence of actinodin, urolithins, and NAD⁺ supplementation reversed cognitive impairments in induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSC) (Human AD patient) models and *Caenorhabditis elegans* animal models of AD. Mitophagy significantly decreased insoluble A40 and A42 levels, neuroinflammation (through microglial phagocytosis), and the density of extracellular senile amyloid plaques in APP/PS1 mice, as well as PHFs/phosphorylated Tau tangles in human neuronal cells (Fang et al., 2019). In another intriguing study, PINK1 expression was shown to be reduced in mouse models of Alzheimer's disease. Overexpression of PINK1 and thus activation of PINK1 dependent signaling

promotes the clearance of dead mitochondria by mediating autophagy signaling and activation of autophagy receptors, resulting in reduced oxidative stress, synaptic dysfunction, and rescue of AD pathology, according to the authors (Du et al., 2017).

Parkin, PINK1, Parkin RBR E3 ubiquitin protein ligase (PARK2), BNIP3L, NDP52, OPTN, unc51like autophagy activating kinase 1 (ULK1), a neighbor of Brca1 gene 1 (NBR1), ATG5, ATG7, ATG8, and LC3 have all been implicated in reversing amyloid toxicity, Tau toxicity, and mitochondrial aber Furthermore, ubiquitination of Gp78, SIAH1, ARIH1, MUL1, and SMURF1 may play a key role in autophagy (Reddy & Oliver, 2019).

4.2 Mitophagy without PINK1/Parkin

To eliminate dead mitochondria, researchers uncovered a number of PINK1/Parkin-independent pathways, including the NiX/BNIP3L pathway, the FUNDC1 pathway, and the OPTN/NDP52 pathway. A NiX region within the BNIP3L domain is responsible for removing dead mitochondria without the participation of Parkin by anchoring the OMM of mitochondria. Hypoxia has been linked to mitochondrial and neural dysfunction in several studies. Dead mitochondria will be removed with the help of FUNDC1 under these conditions. FUNDC1 possesses LC3 interacting motifs (LIM) and is consequently implicated in the production of autophagosomes, which are engaged in mitophagy activity recruitment. Furthermore, autophagy and beclin 1 regulator 1 (AMBRA1), aminobutyric acid A receptors (GABARAP), pleckstrin homology domain containing family M member 1 (PLEKHM1), and homotypic fusion and protein sorting (HOPS) all covalently interact with LC3 via LIM, inciting mitophagic activity (Chen et al., 2015, 2016; Itoh et al., 2013; Kerr et al., 2017; Sandoval et al., 2008; Strappazzon et al., 2015).

In one research, PINK1 was shown to play a critical function in recruiting OPTN and NDP52 to trigger mitophagy without the participation of Parkin. These NDP52 and OPTN interacted with autophagy proteins such as ULK1, double FYVE domain containing protein 1 (DFCP1), and wild type p53 induced phosphatase (WIP1) in the clearance of dead mitochondria through upstream contact with LC3 in the second stage (Lazarou et al., 2015). This research also found that Parkin does not have a function in mitophagy (Lazarou et al., 2015). These findings prompted the researchers to investigate if overexpressed PINK1 protects mutant APP mice. Damaged/dysfunctional mitochondria were removed in another recent work using overexpressed PINK1 and its autophagy receptors, such as NADP52 and OPTN (Du et al., 2017). Furthermore, after suppressing PINK1, the researchers examined the data and observed no reversal of amyloid disease in mutant APP mice (Du et al., 2017). As a result, our data supported the idea that mitophagy may occur without Parkin or p62.

Different investigations have highlighted the importance of oxidized nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD⁺), poly (ADPribose) polymerase 1 (PARP1), and DNA doublestrand breaks in mitophagy (Fang, 2019; Kerr et al., 2017). Normally, NAD⁺ and NADH + H⁺ are required for glucose oxidation in glycolysis, the TCA cycle, and OXOPHOS. A large number of ATPs are necessary for neuronal survival and proper function. When NAD⁺ levels are low, it impairs the health of neuronal mitochondria because PGC1/SIRT1 signaling is hampered. Reduced levels of NAD⁺ may also lead to a loss of mitophagy activity in neuronal cells by influencing PARP under DNA damage, since they interact with each other through doublestrand breaks of NAD/PARP, PARP, or NAD/DNA (Fang, 2019; Kerr et al., 2017). AMBRA1 interacts with LC3 and induces both Parkin-mediated and Parkin-independent mitophagy in mammals, whereas Nix/BNIP3L, FUNDC1, and AMBRA1 operate as

mitophagy receptors. Furthermore, in hypoxic settings, FUNDC1 controls Drp1 and OPA1 to control mitophagy. Finally, mitophagy receptors containing the coupled proteins are delivered to LC3 and GABARAP (nascent autophagosomes) for ultimate autophagy activity with HOPS and PLKHM1 (lysosome LC3 binding proteins) (Kerr et al., 2017).

4.3 Drp1 activity modifiers

4.3.1 Genetic approach

An increase in ROS associated with severe mitochondria bioenergetic dysfunction was linked to a large rise in Drp1 and A levels, according to Manczak et al. (2016). In contrast, researchers found attenuated mitochondria bioenergetics, reduced soluble A, Tau neurofibrillary tangles, and reduced mRNA expression of mitochondrial fission genes in cortical tissues of 6-month-old double mutant APP—Drp1 +/-mice (Manczak et al., 2011, 2016) as well as double mutant Tau—Drp1 +/-mice (Kandimalla & Reddy, 2016). (Kandimalla & Reddy, 2016; Oliver & Reddy, 2019a).

Reddy's lab used quantitative real-time PCR, immunoblotting, and immunostaining to evaluate the expression of mitophagy and autophagy-related mRNA/proteins in two separate experiments. Manczak et al. (2018) looked into the negative effects of mutant APP on mitochondrial functioning, mitophagy/autophagy, neural plasticity, synaptic plasticity, mitochondrial fusion–fission balance, and mitochondrial biogenesis in the Tg2576 Hippocampus (AD mouse model for mutant APP). The researchers found a considerable loss of mitochondrial functioning, as measured by increased peroxide levels, HNE levels, and Drp1 GTPase activity, in this investigation. Reduced cytochrome C oxidase activity and ATP levels were also indicators of mitochondrial function loss. Intriguingly, researchers discovered a fission–fusion imbalance (Drp1, Fis1, and Mfn1, Mfn2, Opa1), as well as a defect in mitochondrial biogenesis. In the hippocampus of the animal models studied, mitophagy (PINK1 and TERT) and autophagy (LC3B and ATG5) were likewise decreased. In addition, decreased dendritic spines were linked to deficiencies in hippocampus learning and memory. After developing amyloid pathology in 12-month-old APP mutant mice, all of these alterations were found (Manczak et al., 2018). In a separate investigation, researchers identified a failure in autophagy and mitophagy pathways in the clearing of dead mitochondria and mitochondria debris in mutant APPHT22 cells (Reddy et al., 2018).

In a neoteric PD investigation, researchers were able to initiate mitophagy without involving the PINK1/Parkin pathway. The NiX-operated mitophagy pathway was used to correct the mitochondrial dysfunctions in this investigation, and the results were verified in PD patient cell lines using a PINK1 knockout condition. When NiX was overexpressed, it caused mitochondrial ATP synthesis to speed up (Koentjoro et al., 2017).

Autophagy and mitophagy are normally controlled by the tumor suppressor protein p53. Goiran et al. (2018) discovered that nuclear p53 inhibits the transcription of PINK1 mRNA, which has been demonstrated to have a p53-inhibiting impact on NDP52, OPTN, and LC3 expression in human cells. HSP60, TOM20, and TIM23 proteins were all shown to be downregulated at the same time (Goiran et al., 2018). HSP60, on the other hand, is a mitochondrial matrix chaperonin, TOM22 is a TOM complex receptor, and TIM23 is the channel forming component of the TIM23 protein import channel in the IMM. Because the two processes can be coregulated, their decline might indicate that nuclear p53 in combination with reduced mitophagy might result in decreased mitochondrial biogenesis. The clearance of dead mitochondria for neuronal survival in PD cells was also characterized by the other

mitophagy route, BNIP3L/NiX, and it was suggested that BNIP3L may operate as a substrate for the PARK2 pathway in PINK/PARK2 driven mitophagy pathway. For neuronal survival, BNIP3L binds NBR1 on dead mitochondria via ubiquitination of BNIP3L by PARK2 (Gao et al., 2015).

Lin et al. (2017) revealed that Parkin/PARK2 had no involvement in regulating mitophagy in the clearance of defective and dead mitochondria to repair the toxicity caused by Alzheimer's disease and other neurodegenerative disorders, but that this may happen via a syntaphilin stress-releasing mechanism.

Several research groups, including ours, have demonstrated that small molecule Drp1 inhibitors can be utilized to reverse the pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease. By restoring mitochondrial fission/fusion equilibrium and boosting mitochondrial biogenesis, small compounds like Mdivi1, SS31, DDQ, and Dynasore have been shown to improve mitochondrial function and general brain health. Recent study has revealed the impacts of these small compounds in experimental models of Alzheimer's disease.

4.4.2.2 Small compounds with a mitochondrial target

Mdivi1 (Mitochondrial Division Inhibitor 1) is a tiny drug that inhibits Drp1 GTPase. Mdivi1 increases mitochondrial activity by decreasing Drp1, according to previous research from Reddy's lab (Manczak & Reddy, 2015; Reddy, Williams et al., 2017). Mdivi1 lowers A β -induced mitochondrial fragmentation and enhances mitochondrial biogenesis and respiration (as evaluated by the seahorse efflux analyzer) in mouse neuroblastoma (N2a) cells, according to one research (Reddy, Williams et al., 2017).

Mdivi1 treatment also inhibited fission genes (Drp1 and Fis1), increased fusion genes (Mfn1, Mfn2, and Opa1), and activated biogenesis genes, according to the researchers (PGC1, Nrf1, Nrf2, and TFAM). When compared to control groups, this group also showed outstanding TEM pictures of mitochondria, which suggested a considerable improvement in mitochondrial morphology in terms of both quantity and size. Baek et al. (2017) found that giving Mdivi1 to AD mice (APP/PS10) reduced mitochondrial fragmentation, reduced ROS generation, decreased mitochondrial depolarization, and enhanced synaptic function (Baek et al., 2017). Bordt and colleagues (2017), on the other hand, claimed that Mdivi1 reversibly suppresses respiration at complex I and that Mdivi1's effects on respiration and ROS are independent of Drp1. Mdivi1 might be a viable therapeutic intervention in neurodegenerative illnesses including Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and ALS since mitochondrial dysfunction is a common symptom.

SzetoSchiller

SzetoSchiller (SS) peptides are tiny compounds with alternating aromatic groups, four amino acids (one of which is a 2', 6' dimethyltyrosine residue), and a positively charged cation (Oliver & Reddy, 2019a). Because of their positive charge and lipophilic characteristics of aliphatic chains and hydrophobic aromatic rings, these peptides target the mitochondrion (Oliver & Reddy, 2019a). The interaction of SS31 with cardiolipin of the inner mitochondrial membrane allows cytochrome C to continue its activity in the electron transport chain, according to a recent study. Calkins et al. (2011) found that adding SS31 to APP mice primary neurons reversed mitochondrial dysfunction, synaptic abnormalities, and irregular mitochondrial transport activities. Furthermore, SS31 was shown to minimize the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in another investigation. Treatment with SS31 enhanced

mitochondrial structure, biogenesis, and function, decreased ROS levels, and boosted the expression of synaptic markers in striatal neurons that persistently express mutant Huntington's disease, according to research by Yin et al. (2016).

The protective impact of SS31 in transgenic AD mice (APP mice) was investigated in an intriguing work by Reddy, Manczak et al. (2017). The authors first tested the permeability of the blood–brain barrier and the ability of SS31 to reach mitochondria by giving mice SS31 intraperitoneally twice a week for two weeks. They found adequate levels of SS31 in the plasma and brain of the SS31-treated mice, indicating that SS31 crosses the blood–brain barrier and reaches neuronal mitochondria. The scientists also determined the expression patterns of genes involved in mitochondrial fission and fusion biogenesis. They discovered that treatment with SS31 resulted in a substantial drop in mitochondrial fission genes and an increase in the expression of fusion and biogenesis genes at both the mRNA and protein levels, contributing to improved overall mitochondrial quality.

In mice treated with SS31, there was also a substantial drop in ROS levels, an increase in cytochrome C activity, and an increase in ATP levels, indicating improved mitochondrial function. Overall, this study was well-organized and revealed the protective effect of SS31 for possible therapeutic uses in Alzheimer's disease. In addition, in mouse neuroblastoma cells overexpressing full-length A, the synergistic protective impact of Mdivi1 and SS31 was investigated (Reddy, Manczak et al., 2017). This study discovered that combining Mdivi1 and SS31 therapies improved mitochondrial and neural protection. The levels of A in treated cells were likewise much lower, as assessed by ELISA. To further validate this notion, a thorough investigation employing transgenic mouse models is required.

Diethyl (3,4-dihydroxyphenethylamino) (quinolin-4-yl) methylphosphonate (DDQ)

DDQ has been proposed as a new Drp1 inhibitor (Kuruva et al., 2017). In silico, molecular docking studies anticipated that it would inhibit Drp1 and its connection with the A complex. They also generated and tested this molecule's therapeutic potential in human SHSY5Y cells treated with A peptides. They discovered that this chemical blocked Drp1 GTPase, preventing mitochondrial fragmentation caused by A. (as evident from the TEM images). The protective impact of this chemical on mitochondrial health and biogenesis also resulted in a decrease in the expression of mitochondrial fission genes and an increase in the expression of fusion genes, according to the scientists. DDQ treatment also resulted in a considerable reduction in A levels in SHSY5Y cell cultures. All of the findings suggest that this chemical might be used to treat Alzheimer's disease and other neurodegenerative disorders (Oliver & Reddy, 2019a). To classify this molecule as an efficient Drp1 inhibitor, more research is needed.

Dynasore is a brand of Dynasore.

Dynasore is an endocytic pathway dynamin GTPase inhibitor that prevents the division or production of dynamin-dependent endocytic vesicles (Oliver & Reddy, 2019a). Dynasore inhibits the GTPase activity of Dynamin1, Dynamin 2, and Drp1 in vitro, according to Macia et al. (2006). In mice, pretreatment with 1 M Dynasore was shown to protect them against ischemia/reperfusion damage (Reddy, 2014). Pretreatment with Dynasore also inhibited ROS-induced mitochondrial fission, enhanced cell survival, and decreased cellular ATP depletion in culture cardiomyocytes (Reddy, 2014). We hypothesized that by restoring mitochondrial fission/fusion equilibrium and avoiding ROS-induced mitochondrial fragmentation, this chemical may have a neuroprotective impact on Alzheimer's disease. To further support these hypotheses, concrete results are required.

Finally, we conclude that small compounds that act as Drp1 inhibitors have therapeutic promise in the treatment of neurodegenerative illnesses by lowering mitochondrial abnormalities and restoring mitochondrial function by lowering oxidative stress. We also believe that innovative forms of these small compounds, such as nanoparticles, might increase their bioavailability and tissue targeting. Furthermore, calorie restriction, mitochondrial-targeted antioxidant compounds, and exercise have all been shown to be effective therapeutic strategies for attracting mitophagy-associated proteins to eliminate defective or dead mitochondria while preserving healthy mitochondria. Mitophagy activation in the prevention of Alzheimer's disease pathogenesis: Intermittent fasting, Omega fatty acid meals, calorie restriction diets, mitophagy inducers, mitochondrial-targeted (antioxidant) tiny molecules (MTA), and Drp1 activity regulators may all help prevent AD development by improving mitochondrial health.

5. IN NEURODEGENERATIVE DISEASES, THE UBIQUITIN-PROTEASOME SYSTEM FAILURE

The process of ubiquitin protein conjugation with the Lys residue of the target substrate is known as ubiquitination. The ubiquitin-proteasome system (UPS) or the lysosomal degradation pathway use this mechanism to identify their respective substrates for breakdown. Ubiquitin chains are used to identify misfolded proteins and faulty or damaged cell organelles so that autophagy may recognize them and degrade them. As a result, the UPS system is critical in detecting and removing damaged cell organelles and misfolded proteins. The failure of the UPS system might be a factor in the formation of NFTs and A plaques in neurodegenerative illnesses like Alzheimer's disease (Heo & Rutter, 2011; Herrmann et al., 2013; Ross et al., 2015).

In an AD investigation, hyperphosphorylated Tau was shown to be ubiquitinated in paired helical filaments in brain samples from individuals with the disease (Mori et al., 1987), indicating a neuronal effort to remove ubiquitinated Tau proteins. However, it is crucial to note that the activity of the proteasome is hampered in diseases such as Alzheimer's disease (Keller et al., 2000), which might explain why ubiquitinated Tau protein clearance fails. Some scientists believe that the activity of the proteasome declines with age. However, Keller and coworkers (2000) found a significant decrease in chymotrypsin and postglutamyl peptidase activity in the parahippocampal gyrus, superior and middle temporal gyri, and inferior parietal lobule in brain samples from Alzheimer's patients. In age-matched controls, no significant drop in proteasome activity was seen, throwing out this theory as a myth in terms of the CNS in humans. The activity of the proteasome was observed to be preferentially impaired in locations with increased NFT accumulation, such as the hippocampus and parahippocampal gyrus (Mori et al., 1987).

Excessive oxidative stress has also been shown to impede proteasome function, which might be another cause for the failure of proteasome function in Alzheimer's disease. The specific protein targets of ubiquitination that accumulate in insoluble deposits in different disorders appear to play major roles in their respective neurodegenerative processes: Tau is ubiquitinated in AD, synuclein is ubiquitinated in PD and dementia with Lewy bodies, and transactivation is ubiquitinated in ALS and frontotemporal lobar degeneration with ubiquitinonly inclusions (FTLNU) in ALS and frontotemporal lobar degeneration with ubi (Ihara et al., 2012).

Furthermore, *in vitro* studies and research on AD patient brain samples show that while levels of and subunits of the proteasome do not decrease, their activity is impeded either owing to hyperphosphorylated Tau buildup at the 19s or 26s cap regions (Keck et al., 2003). Furthermore, soluble A oligomers have been shown to impede proteasome activity (Bence et al., 2001). Both hyperphosphorylated Tau and soluble A forms contribute to the UPS system's lower activity in AD pathogenesis.

5.1 Role of miRs in mitochondrial biogenesis, dynamics, and mitophagy MiRs are a family of small, single-stranded noncoding RNAs that play a role in the posttranscriptional regulation of coding mRNAs, either by repressing or degrading their translation. They also play a role in mitochondrial biogenesis. Different miRs have both protective and harmful effects on Alzheimer's disease, according to new findings (Amakiri et al., 2019; Reddy, Williams et al., 2017). Some of these miRs are known to control mitochondrial biogenesis, dynamics, and mitophagy through acting on them (Amakiri et al., 2019). Recent research on mitochondrial miRs has provided new information on their role in controlling mitochondrial dynamics in various pathological situations (Dewanjee & Bhattacharjee, 2018; John et al., 2020; Reddy, Manczak, et al., 2017; Song et al., 2019). 169 miRs were discovered in mitochondria by Barrey and colleagues (2011), and they are expected to control polypeptide genes in the mitochondrial genome, energy generation, and oxidative phosphorylation. PremiRs are thought to be transcribed in the cytosol and carried to mitochondria, where they are processed and transferred back to the cytosol to control the transcription of additional cytosolic mRNA, or they can operate directly on mRNA generated from mitochondrial DNA (Duarte et al., 2014). These miRs can affect mitochondrial dynamics either directly (by acting on mitochondrial fission or fusion machinery, like miR761) or indirectly (by acting on proteins affecting mitochondrial biogenesis, like miR499). However, how this miR is delivered to mitochondria and if any miR is generated from mitochondrial genes are unknown. MiR15b, miR23a/b, miR107, miR132, miR143, and miR330, which have been reported to be neuroprotective and can prevent mitochondrial malfunction and A formation, were found to be downregulated in neural cells of Alzheimer's patients (Amakiri et al., 2019; John et al., 2020). MiR98 can minimize A formation and alleviate mitochondrial dysfunctions by blocking the Notch pathway by targeting hairy and enhancer of split (Hes) linked with YRPW motif protein 2 (HEY2) (Amakiri et al., 2019).

Catanesi et al. (2020) found that miR98 promotes A formation by targeting insulinlike growth factor 1, implicating a pathogenic function in Alzheimer's disease. MiR15a, miR34a, miR126, miR181a, miR2103p, miR425, and miR424 remained increased in Alzheimer's disease, implying structural and functional loss of mitochondria and being discovered to have pathogenic roles in the disease (Catanesi et al., 2020; John et al., 2020). Mitophagy, which is elevated in Alzheimer's disease, is negatively controlled by miR27a and miR101 (John et al., 2020).

Mitochondrial miRs are critical regulators of mitochondrial dynamics of fusion–fission imbalance in Alzheimer's disease. Several miRs that govern mitochondrial dynamics have been identified as important regulators of mitochondrial dynamic proteins in Alzheimer's disease (John et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2019; Kumar & Reddy, 2019; Lima et al., 2017; Reddy, Manczak, et al., 2017). Synaptic miRs have also been identified as important regulators in Alzheimer's disease, with the ability to regulate mitochondrial activity and energy balance (Kumar & Reddy, 2020). Their specific functions in mitochondrial function,

however, have yet to be determined. Individual miRs' roles in mitochondrial biogenesis, dynamics, and mitophagy during Alzheimer's disease deserve more investigation.

6. Conclusions

In vitro and in vivo AD models, mitochondrial dysfunction is the key characteristic that inhibits neuronal function and leads to A toxicity and phosphorylated Tau toxicity. Excessive mitochondrial division might be inhibited, or mitophagy might be increased, to correct AD pathogenesis. However, there are still unsolved riddles in the production of senile plaques and NFTs, and there are no comprehensive unifying principles in the pathophysiology of Alzheimer's disease. Some researchers believe A toxicity and Tau toxicity are upstream processes in mitochondrial dysfunction, while others believe it is a downstream cascade of events involving aberrant mitochondria. In PINK1 signaling, there are various mitophagy routes for the removal of dead mitochondria; some are controlled by Parkin, while others are not. According to other researchers, Drp1, Mfn1/2, PINK1, or Parkin play no part in mitophagy cleaning malfunctioning mitochondria; hence, more research is needed to unravel the riddle of mitophagy signaling pathways for clearing dead mitochondria and preserving high-quality mitochondria. Mitophagy activity therapeutic approaches would be effective in correcting AD pathogenesis.

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